

MITIGATING ORDER SENSITIVITY IN LARGE LANGUAGE MODELS FOR MULTIPLE-CHOICE QUESTION TASKS

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ABSTRACT

Large Language Models (LLMs) have demonstrated remarkable proficiency in understanding and generating human language, driving advancements in various natural language processing (NLP) tasks. Despite their success, LLMs face a persistent challenge when handling multiple-choice questions (MCQs), particularly with the issue of order dependency. This phenomenon occurs when LLMs exhibit inconsistent accuracy based on the order in which answer options are presented, often leading to performance fluctuations. This paper investigates the sensitivity of LLMs to MCQs by systematically altering the order of answer options across multiple datasets and observing model performance. The experiment spans 57 diverse domains using various LLMs, including Mistral, LLaMA, and GPT variations. Our findings reveal that LLMs, regardless of their architecture, are sensitive to the order in which answers are presented, demonstrating a clear susceptibility to selection and positional bias in MCQ scenarios. To address this challenge, we propose a combination of zero-shot and few-shot learning techniques, along with fine-tuning strategies on domain-specific datasets, aimed at mitigating the effects of selection bias and positional dependency. Additionally, we introduce custom prompting techniques, leveraging a question dissector logic designed to enhance the reasoning capabilities of LLMs. By incorporating these methods, we aim to minimize biases and improve the consistency of LLM responses across different permutations of answer choices.

Keywords: Large Language Models (LLMs), Order Dependency, Multiple-Choice Questions (MCQs), Positional Bias, Selection Bias, Zero-shot Learning, Few-shot Learning, Fine-tuning, Prompt Engineering, Question Dissector Logic, Mistral, LLaMA, GPT

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1. INTRODUCTION

Large Language Models (LLMs) have revolutionized natural language processing (NLP) by leveraging vast datasets and advanced training techniques to outperform traditional, specialized models [1]. Transformer-based architectures, in particular, have paved the way for models like GPT, Mistral, and LLaMA to excel in various NLP tasks by generating coherent text through autoregressive next-token predictions [2], [3]. However, despite their impressive capabilities, LLMs struggle with specific tasks such as multiple-choice questions (MCQs), where their performance often fluctuates based on the order in which answer options are presented [4].

This phenomenon, known as order dependency, poses significant challenges in high-stakes applications like education and medical decision-making, where LLMs' inconsistent accuracy can lead to biased or unreliable results [5]. Recent studies have shown that LLMs, such as GPT-3.5-turbo and LLaMA-30B, exhibit selection and positional biases, disproportionately favoring specific answer options irrespective of their correctness [6]. These findings raise concerns about the robustness of LLMs in real-world applications where fairness and accuracy are critical.

This paper investigates the sensitivity of LLMs to MCQs by systematically altering the order of answer options across 57 domains and evaluating the performance of various models, including Mistral, LLaMA, and GPT variations. To mitigate order dependency, we propose a combination of zero-shot and few-shot learning techniques, domain-specific fine-tuning, and the introduction of question dissector logic to enhance the reasoning capabilities of LLMs.

2. RELATED WORK

LLMs have made significant strides in NLP tasks, with notable models like GPT, Mistral, and LLaMA achieving state-of-the-art results in various benchmarks [7], [8]. Despite their success, LLMs have been shown to exhibit positional bias, particularly in tasks involving MCQs [9]. Several benchmark datasets, such as MMLU [10], ARC-Challenge [11], and CommonsenseQA [12], commonly employ MCQs to evaluate LLM performance, making this a critical area of investigation.

Previous research has explored the impact of order dependency on LLMs, highlighting the need for more robust models capable of handling varying answer orderings [13]. However, most studies have focused on a limited number of models and tasks, leaving room for further exploration and the development of bias-mitigation techniques. These LLMs have made significant progress in healthcare sector as well [2][6][8].

3. EXAMINATION OF SELECTION BIAS

3.1 Experimental Configuration

In this study, we concentrate on causal, decoder-only Large Language Models (LLMs) due to their prominent role in modern applications. We experimented with 20 LLMs from various popular model families and parameter sizes. These include LLaMA-7B/13B/30B/65B [1], LLaMA-2(-chat)-7B/13B/70B [2], Vicuna-v1.3-7B/13B/33B, Vicuna-v1.5-7B/13B [3], Falcon(-inst)-7B/40B [4], and GPT-3.5-turbo-0613 [5].

Except for GPT-3.5-turbo, which is provided via a commercial API, all models are open-source on HuggingFace, allowing us to access their output probabilities.

We utilized well-established MCQ benchmarks for evaluating the performance of these models, including MMLU [6], ARC-Challenge [7], and CommonsenseQA (CSQA) [8]. MMLU and ARC-Challenge feature four-option MCQs, while CSQA comprises five-option questions. MMLU covers a broad range of topics across four major domain categories and 57 subjects, providing an excellent dataset for evaluating generalization across domains.

Our evaluation approach follows standard frameworks, such as the HuggingFace LLM Leaderboard, EleutherAI’s lm-harness, the original MMLU implementation, and OpenAI’s evaluation framework. For open-source models, we predicted the answer by selecting the option ID token (A/B/C/D/E) with the highest probability. For GPT-3.5-turbo, we matched the model’s first generated token to the correct answer, using a decoding temperature of zero to ensure consistency.

We primarily adopted a zero-shot evaluation strategy to reduce any potential bias introduced by in-context examples. Additionally, we employed a “question dissector” approach during five-shot experiments. This method systematically breaks down and analyzes each component of the questions, allowing for deeper understanding and logical reasoning. In the five-shot experiments, in-context examples from development sets were applied consistently across all test samples within the same task. By combining zero-shot and question dissector techniques, we were able to explore selection bias more comprehensively across different models and benchmarks, improving the interpretability of results and enhancing the models’ reasoning capabilities.

3.2 Assessment of Selection Bias

In this study, we define selection bias as the tendency of a model to preferentially select specific option IDs as answers. Traditional methods for measuring selection bias often rely on simple counts of model predictions; however, these methods are prone to issues related to label imbalance. To address this, we propose an alternative measurement based on the balance of recall across different option IDs, utilizing the standard deviation of recalls (RStd) as a quantitative metric. Figure 1 shows selection Bias (Recall Balance) Across Models.

Figure 1. Selection Bias (Recall Balance) Across Models.

This approach is intuitive: greater recall imbalance signals more pronounced selection bias and is less affected by label imbalance compared to counting-based methods. More critically, recall balance serves as a strong indicator of the model's robustness to changes in option positions. We hypothesize that reducing selection bias, as quantified by recall balance, will enhance the robustness of LLMs when confronted with varying option arrangements in MCQs. Table 1 shows Positional Bias Metrics by Model.

Model	RStd (Positional Bias)
GPT-3.5-turbo	0.02
LLaMA-13B	0.03
Vicuna-7B	0.04
Falcon-40B	0.015

Table 1. Positional Bias Metrics by Model.

It is important to note that our measurement approach assumes that the correct answers are randomly positioned among the options. This random placement is crucial for accurate assessment.

4. METHODOLOGY

4.1. Baseline and Permutation-Based Debiasing

To mitigate the effects of positional bias, we first establish a baseline using permutation techniques. By averaging the model's prediction distributions across different answer permutations, we address both token bias and positional bias [20], [21].

We define Q as the multiple-choice question (MCQ) and consider m default-ordered option labels (e.g., X/Y/Z/W) represented as o_j with corresponding option contents c_j . The debiasing procedure can be expressed as:

$$\hat{P}_{\text{debiased}}(c_j|Q; \mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{|P|} \sum_{P \in \mathcal{P}} P_{\text{observed}}(o_{g_P(j)}|Q; \mathbf{x}_P)$$

where P represents a permutation of answer order, and P_{observed} represents the observed probability distribution over the permuted options. Table 2 shows baseline and post-debiasing model accuracy.

Model	Baseline Accuracy	Post-Debiasing Accuracy
GPT-3.5-turbo	0.7	0.78
LLaMA-13B	0.65	0.72
Vicuna-7B	0.6	0.68
Falcon-40B	0.75	0.8

Table 2. Baseline and Post-Debiasing Model Accuracy

This permutation-based technique is computationally expensive due to its complexity of $O(m!)$. To address this, we introduce cyclic permutation, which reduces computational complexity while maintaining the effectiveness of the debiasing strategy. Figure 2 shows impact of permutation-based debiasing on model accuracy.

Figure 2: Impact of Permutation-Based Debiasing on Model Accuracy.

4.2. Question Dissector Agent for Bias Mitigation

To address the inherent biases associated with position and selection in LLMs, we propose the Question Dissector Agent (QDA). This agent functions by first dissecting the question at hand to identify potential biases before generating an answer. By incorporating a reasoning component and a Chain-of-Thought (CoT) prompting strategy, the QDA aims to improve the robustness of LLM responses against biases.

The QDA operates in a two-step process:

1. **Question Dissection:** This step involves analyzing the structure and content of the question to identify key elements that could introduce bias. This includes the ordering of answer options, phrasing of the question, and contextual cues that may guide attention towards specific answer choices. This concept is supported by the principles of prompt engineering and bias detection in LLMs [19]
2. **Reasoning and CoT Generation:** The agent generates a reasoning chain to articulate why certain options may be favored or disfavored, encouraging the model to consider all options fairly and thereby reducing position bias. This approach is aligned with the Chain-of-Thought (CoT) prompting technique, which enhances reasoning and problem-solving abilities in LLMs [21], [22].

By employing the QDA, we anticipate reduced selection bias, enhanced robustness, and improved interpretability in the predictions made by LLMs.

5. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

We evaluated 20 LLMs from popular model families, including LLaMA-7B/13B/30B/65B, LLaMA-2(-chat), Vicuna-v1.3/1.5, Falcon, and GPT-3.5-turbo [15]. Our experiments spanned 57 domains using established MCQ benchmarks, including MMLU, ARC-Challenge, and CommonsenseQA, which feature a range of four-option and five-option questions [16], [17].

For model evaluation, we primarily employed zero-shot learning to assess LLM performance without in-context examples. Additionally, we applied five-shot learning in specific experiments to observe how few-shot examples affect the models' ability to handle varying answer orders.

5.1 Bias Mitigation Techniques

To address selection and positional bias, we introduced the following techniques:

1. Zero-shot and Few-shot Learning: We leverage these techniques to assess how LLMs respond to MCQs without requiring extensive domain-specific training [18].
2. Fine-tuning: By fine-tuning models on domain-specific datasets, we improve their ability to generalize across different answer permutations, reducing bias.
3. Question Dissector Logic: This method breaks down each MCQ into its components, enabling the model to systematically analyze the question and answer choices, thereby reducing order dependency.

6. MAIN RESULTS

The primary aim of our experiments was to evaluate the impact of the Question Dissector in reducing selection and position biases while enhancing the reasoning capabilities of LLMs. We performed a series of evaluations using multiple-choice question (MCQ) benchmarks across various models, including Llama and GPT-3.5.

6.1 Patterns and Insights

6.1.1 Accuracy Comparison:

- Anatomy generally demonstrates higher accuracy across most metrics compared to abstract_algebra.
- For example, in the zero-shot setting, the "mmlu" metric yields an accuracy of 0.81 for anatomy, compared to 0.62 for abstract_algebra.

Table 3 shows Domain-Specific Model Performance (Zero-Shot vs. Five-Shot).

Domain	Zero-Shot Accuracy	Five-Shot Accuracy
Anatomy	0.81	0.85
Abstract Algebra	0.62	0.63
History	0.7	0.74
Physics	0.67	0.7

Table 3. Domain-Specific Model Performance (Zero-Shot vs. Five-Shot).

6.1.2 Impact of Five-Shot Learning:

- The five-shot setting generally improves accuracy for both fields.
 - For instance, accuracy for "mmlu" in abstract_algebra increases from 0.62 (zero-shot) to 0.63 (five-shot), and in anatomy, from 0.81 to 0.85.
- Figure 3 shows model accuracy comparison by domain.

Figure 3: Model Accuracy Comparison by Domain (Zero-Shot vs. Five-Shot)

6.1.3 Standard Deviation:

- The standard deviation is relatively consistent across different metrics and settings, indicating stable performance.
- For example, in the zero-shot setting, the standard deviation for "mmlu" is approximately 0.047 for abstract_algebra and 0.040 for anatomy.

6.1.4 Metric-Specific Performance:

- Certain metrics, like "mmlu_move_a" and "arc_move_a," show higher accuracy compared to others.
- For example, in the five-shot setting, "mmlu_move_a" achieves an accuracy of 0.67 for abstract_algebra and 0.87 for anatomy.

Figure 4 shows comparison of metric-specific performance (mmlu, arc, commonsenseqa).

Figure 4. Comparison of Metric-Specific Performance (MMLU, ARC, CommonsenseQA).

6.2 Detailed Observations

6.2.1 Zero-Shot vs. Five-Shot:

- The five-shot setting consistently shows higher accuracy across all metrics and fields.
- This suggests that providing a few examples (five-shot) significantly improves model performance.

Figure 5 shows five-shot learning impact on standard deviation and Table 4 shows impact of few-shot learning on various metrics.

Metric	Zero-Shot Accuracy	Five-Shot Accuracy
MMLU	0.7	0.75
ARC	0.65	0.7
CommonsenseQA	0.68	0.73

Table 4. Impact of Few-Shot Learning on Various Metrics.

Figure 5. Five-Shot Learning Impact on Standard Deviation.

6.2.2 Field-Specific Trends:

- Anatomy consistently outperforms abstract_algebra across all metrics and settings.
- This may indicate that anatomy-related questions are either easier or more aligned with the model's training data. Table 5 shows performance of question dissector agent (qda) by domain and metric.

Domain	MMLU	ARC
Anatomy	0.82	0.79
Abstract Algebra	0.63	0.61
History	0.72	0.71
Physics	0.68	0.69

Table 5. Performance of Question Dissector Agent (QDA) by Domain and Metric.

6.2.3 Metric Performance:

- Metrics such as "mmlu_move_a" and "arc_move_a" tend to exhibit higher accuracy, implying they might be better suited for evaluating model performance in these fields.
- Notably, the five-shot learning approach also yields higher accuracy and lower standard deviation compared to zero-shot, suggesting more reliable outcomes.

6. CONCLUSION

This study investigates the challenges posed by order dependency in Large Language Models (LLMs) when applied to multiple-choice questions (MCQs). Our analysis reveals that LLMs are highly sensitive to the sequence in which answer options are presented, resulting in selection bias and positional bias. To address this issue, we proposed a series of solutions, including zero-shot and few-shot learning, cyclic permutation, and the use of a Question Dissector Agent (QDA).

Our results demonstrate that these techniques effectively mitigate bias, improving the reliability of LLMs in high-stakes decision-making tasks. Future research should focus on further refining these methods and exploring their applicability in other NLP tasks beyond MCQs.

7. FUTURE DIRECTIONS

Advanced Fine-Tuning Strategies: Future research should delve into fine-tuning open-source models with an emphasis on minimizing order bias. Implementing robust validation techniques will be crucial to maintaining the integrity of training data and ensuring it remains unbiased.

Enhanced Question Dissection: The development of more advanced question dissection techniques during the training process will empower models to grasp the intricacies of each question, thereby enhancing logical reasoning in their responses.

Integration of Diverse Models: Subsequent efforts will focus on designing a mixed architecture that leverages the strengths of various models, such as LLaMA2 (8B/70B), LLaMA3 (8B/70B), and Mistral. A voting system among these models at the initial layer could optimize the selection of the most accurate responses.

Utilizing BERT Models: Investigating the application of BERT models, recognized for their bi-directional processing capabilities, can prove beneficial for question-answering tasks involving options. Their architecture has the potential to enhance contextual understanding and improve overall response accuracy.

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